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**FAMILY LIFE AND PEER INFLUENCE AS CORRELATES OF ACADEMIC
ADJUSTMENT OF STUDENTS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT IN OYO STATE,
NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This paper examines family life and peer influence as correlates of academic adjustment of students with visual impaired. The purpose of the study is to identify the relationship, joint contribution and relative contribution of family life and peer influence to academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. The findings show that, family life and peer influence has significant impact on the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. The study recommends that, parents should ensure that all necessary support needed by their children with visual impairment must be taking care of so as to help them in their academic pursuit coupled with positive peer influence.

Key word: family life, peer influence, academic adjustment, student with visual impairment

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INTRODUCTION

Parent's involvement plays a significant role in the general development of their school age children. Part of the parental roles helps in developing the learning habits of their children as we help in their academic adjustment. Such roles include:

- Parents as Parent,
- Parents as Teachers
- Parents as Educational decision makers and
- Parents as Advocate. (Turble, 2003)

In a study by Adeyemo (2010), it was highlighted that a supportive family background plays a crucial role in the success and happiness of children, especially those with visual impairment. Factors like parental educational background, income, exposure, and family dynamics significantly impact the academic and social lives of these students. Family factors, along with peer pressure, can influence the academic adjustments of students with visual impairment, making it important to investigate these aspects further.

Various family factors, such as the family environment, size, parents' educational qualifications, and family type, can positively or negatively affect a child's academic performance. The family serves as the primary agent of socialization, influencing the child's self-worth and academic attainment. Additionally, family size can impact a student's academic performance, with smaller families often associated with higher educational attainment.

Visual impairment is a condition that leads to reduced visual performance, resulting in functional limitations and difficulties in performing daily tasks, like reading and writing, even with refractive correction.

Moreover, individuals with visual impairment can enhance their abilities to perform visual tasks through compensatory low vision aids and environmental adjustments, as pointed out by Abodunrin and Abodunrin (2020). Perception of the learning environment plays a significant role in students' academic achievement and overall well-being. Students who perceive their environment as supportive and conducive are more likely to exhibit achievement-oriented behavior and put in more effort. Successful adjustment within the educational system requires understanding, fitting in, and mastering the system. Visual impairment in childhood is a low prevalence condition, ranging from 3 per 10.000 in socioeconomically developed countries, to 15 per 10.000 in poorer countries (Rahi and Cable, 2003; Resnikoff et al., 2004). It often coexists with other impairments or disabilities (Flanagan, Jackson, and Hill, 2003; Rahi and Cable, 2003; Salt and Sargent, 2014).

The presence of a VI affects children's global development (motor, cognitive and psychosocial aspects), restrains their participation in social activities, and generally worsens their quality of life (Rainey, Elsmann, van Nispen, van Leeuwen, and van Rens, 2016). Vision is an important factor in the learning process that also serves as a non-verbal

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communication channel governing social interaction. In older children, vision is especially related not only to academic achievements but also to other aspects of life, such as sports practice, autonomy, relationships, etc. (Checa, Díaz, & Pallero 2003). The limitations and participation restrictions of children with VI may further increase if they suffer from co-existing disabilities. In such a case, it is critical to detect visual function or visual system anomalies in order to strengthen the ratio ability vs. disability. However, this strategy is not always a priority for healthcare providers or even for families (Woodhouse, Davies, McAvinchey, and Ryan, 2014).

Academic adjustment for students with visual impairment involves balancing their academic tasks with their visual limitations. This process starts when they enter school, concentrate on instructional tasks, interact with their academic environment, and achieve within that context. The ability to adjust to challenges resulting from visual impairment depends on acceptance, recognition, and accommodation from parents, family, peers, and society.

While family and peer support are crucial, they should also ensure an enabling environment for the child's maximum benefit. Family and peer influence significantly impact students' academic performance, and factors like socioeconomic status can affect test scores and cognitive development. The study aims to explore the correlation among family life, peer influence and academic adjustment of students with visual impairment in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine family life and peer influence as correlates of academic adjustment of students with visual impairment in Ibadan, Oyo state. Specifically, the purpose of the study is to:

1. Examine the relationship between the independent variable (Family Life and Peer Influence) and the dependent variable (Academic Adjustment) of students with Visual Impairment.
2. Identify the joint contribution of family life and peer influence to the academic adjustment of students with Visual Impairments.
3. Evaluate the relative contribution of family life peer influence to the academic adjustment of students with Visual Impairments.

Research Questions

The following research question guides the study:

1. What is the relationship between the independent variables (family life and peer influence) and the dependent variable (academic adjustment) of students with visual impairment?
2. What is the composite contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable (academic adjustment) of students with visual impairment?
3. What is the relative contribution of the independent variables to dependent variable (academic adjustment) of students with visual impairment?

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METHODOLOGY

This research work adopts the survey research design. The sample for the study comprises of 100 respondents who were students with visual impairment including male and female with total blindness and low vision. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the target population. The researcher used 4-Likert point questionnaires to gather information from students with visual impairments. The questionnaires consisted of section A, B, C and D. Section A consists of Bio-data information of the respondents, section B consists of questions relating to family life, Section C has to do with influence while Section D consists of questions relating to academic adjustments. Pearson's Product moment correlation (PPMC) and multiple regression was used in analyzing the data

Results

Socio Demographic Distribution of Respondents

Table 1: Frequency distribution of respondents by sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	39	39.0
Female	61	61.0
Total	100.0	100.0

Table 1 shows that 39.0% students are male and 61.0% are female

Table 2 Frequency distribution of respondents by present academic level

Present academic level	Frequency	Percentage
Primary school leaving certificate	65	65.0
Ordinary level (O'level)	15	15.0
Higher institution	20	20.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 shows 65.0% of the students had primary school leaving certificate, 15.0% had secondary school leaving certificate, and 20.0% had tertiary education

Table 3: Frequency distribution of respondents by onset of visual impairment

Onset of visual impairment	Frequency	Percentage
Congenital	25	25.0
Acquired	75	75.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 shows that 25.0% students had congenital visual impairment and 75.0% had acquired onset of visual impairment

Answering of Research Questions

Research question one: What is the relationship between the independent variables (Family life and Peer influence) and dependent variable (academic adjustment) of students with visual impairment in Ibadan, Oyo State

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Table 4 Zero Order correlation showing the relationship between family life, peer influence, and academic adjustment of students with visual impairment

	Academic adjustment	Family life	Peer influence
Academic adjustment	1		
Family life	.489* (.000)	1	
Peer influence	.282* (.004)	.240* (.000)	1
Mean (\bar{x})	24.5300	30.9100	28.6900
S.D	3.21126	4.36259	4.23238

* Sig. at 0.05 level

Table 4 shows that there is a significant relationship between academic adjustment of students with visual impairment and family life ($r=.489$, $p(.000)<.05$), Peer influence ($r=.282$, $p(.004)<.05$) respectively. Hence, family life and peer influence enhance the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Research question two: What is the joint contribution of the independent variable (Family life and Peer influence) to the dependent variable (Academic adjustment of student with visual impairment) in Ibadan?

Table 5 Summary of Regression analysis showing the joint effect of family life and peer influence on academic adjustment of student with visual impairment

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate			
.518	.268	.253	2.77527			
ANOVA						
Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Regression	273.807	2	136.903	17.775	.001	Sig.
Residual	747.103	97	7.702			
Total	1020.910	99				

Table 5 shows the joint effect of family life and peer influence on academic adjustment of student with visual impairment. The table also shows a coefficient of multiple correlation $R = .518$ and a multiple R^2 of .268. This means that 26.8% of the variance was accounted for by the two predictor variables when taken together. The significance of the composite contribution was tested at $\alpha = 0.05$. The table also shows that the analysis of variance for the regression yielded F-ratio of 17.775(significant at 0.05 level). This implies that the joint contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable was significant and that other variables not included in this model may have accounted for the remaining variance.

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Research question three: What are the relative contribution of the independent variable (Family life and Peer influence) to the dependent variable (Academic adjustment of students with visual impairment)?

Table 6 Summary of regression analysis showing the relative contribution of family life and peer influence on academic adjustment of student with visual impairment

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig. p
	B	Std. Error	Beta Contribution		
(Constant)	10.551	2.472		4.268	.000
Family life	.329	.066	.447	5.001	.000
Peer influence	.132	.068	.174	1.950	.054

Table 6 shows that the relative contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable, expressed as beta weights, viz: Family life ($\beta = .447$, $p < .05$) and Peer influence ($\beta = .174$, $p < .05$). Hence, family life and peer influence were significant i.e. could independently and significantly predict academic adjustment of student with visual impairment in the study.

Table 7: Measure of family life as a predictor of academic adjustment of students with visual impairment

s/n	Family life	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D
1	My family supports emotionally me to settle in school	2 2.0%	2 2.0%	47 47.0%	49 49.0%	3.43	0.640
2	I have the full backing of my family in pursuing my academic career	6 6.0%	5 5.0%	47 47.0%	42 42.0%	3.25	0.809
3	My siblings give me the needed assistance for my academic	15 15.0%	15 15.0%	37 37.0%	33 33.0%	2.88	1.037
4	My parents help me to adjust in school	21 21.0%	9 9.0%	39 39.0%	31 31.0%	2.80	1.101
5	I can rely on my family to get me financial support	13 13.0%	11 11.0%	24 24.0%	52 52.0%	3.15	1.067
6	My family is concern about my academic	12 12.0%	7 7.0%	39 39.0%	42 42.0%	3.11	0.984
7	I do receive visitation from my family	9 9.0%	7 7.0%	52 52.0%	32 32.0%	3.07	0.868
8	My paternal family is concern about my academic	18 18.0%	12 12.0%	35 35.0%	35 35.0%	2.87	1.089
9	My maternal family seems bothered for my academic	6 6.0%	3 3.0%	56 56.0%	35 35.0%	3.20	0.765
10	My family discusses my academic adjustment most often	3 3.0%	7 7.0%	62 62.0%	28 28.0%	3.15	0.672
Weighted Mean =3.09							

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Table 7 shows the measure of family life in relations to the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

Table 8 Measure of peer influence as a predictor of academic adjustment of students with visual impairment

s/n	Peer influence	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D
1	My friends have a lot to do for my academic adjustment	25 25.0%	2 2.0%	30 30.0%	43 43.0%	2.91	1.207
2	Most of the things taught me by my teachers are been explained to me better by my friends	7 7.0%	3 3.0%	45 45.0%	45 45.0%	3.28	0.830
3	My academic needs have been met adequately by my course mates	23 23.0%	19 19.0%	37 37.0%	21 21.0%	2.56	1.067
4	Learning by abstraction becomes easier through my peers	31 31.0%	21 21.0%	30 30.0%	18 18.0%	2.35	1.104
5	I have special person to relate with academically	25 25.0%	12 12.0%	29 29.0%	34 34.0%	2.72	1.181
6	I do enjoy free and often learning services by my friends	15 15.0%	14 14.0%	29 29.0%	42 42.0%	2.98	1.082
7	Learning effectively has been made possible by my peers	14 14.0%	7 7.0%	39 39.0%	40 40.0%	3.05	1.019
8	I have a special person who is real source of comfort to me academically	14 14.0%	12 12.0%	47 47.0%	27 27.0%	2.87	0.971
9	My friends have helped me pass an exam before	9 9.0%	14 14.0%	55 55.0%	22 22.0%	2.90	0.847
10	There is a special person with whom I can share my joys and sorrows	5 5.0%	7 7.0%	64 64.0%	24 24.0%	3.07	0.714

Weighted Mean =2.87

Table 8 shows the measure of peer influence in relations to the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

Table 9 Measures of academic adjustment among students with visual impairment in Ibadan

s/n	Academic adjustment	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D
1	I find it easy to cope in school	67 67.0%	3 3.0%	10 10.0%	20 20.0%	1.83	1.248
2	My school environment is disability friendly	4 4.0%	3 3.0%	18 18.0%	75 75.0%	3.64	0.732
3	Am always frustrated whenever am in school	12 12.0%	14 14.0%	72 72.0%	2 2.0%	2.64	0.718
4	The relationship between me and my teacher is like a cat and rat	38 38.0%	49 49.0%	5 5.0%	8 8.0%	1.83	0.853
5	My challenges increases when am in school	60 60.0%	15 15.0%	14 14.0%	11 11.0%	1.76	1.065

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6	My teacher did not believe in my academic career	36 36.0%	14 14.0%	27 27.0%	23 23.0%	2.37	1.195
7	My teacher always provide solution to my academic needs	19 19.0%	32 32.0%	31 31.0%	18 18.0%	2.48	1.000
8	My impairment limits my academic adjustment	20 20.0%	20 20.0%	31 31.0%	29 29.0%	2.69	1.098
9	My school environment is academically friendly	23 23.0%	15 15.0%	51 51.0%	11 11.0%	2.50	0.969
10	The training I received in school has helped me in my academic work	7 7.0%	8 8.0%	71 71.0%	14 14.0%	2.92	0.706
Weighted Mean =2.47							

Table 9 shows the measure of academic adjustment of students with visual impairment in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

The research findings indicate that family life and peer influence have a significant impact on the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment, aligning with Abodunrin and Komolafe's (2017) perspective. The study emphasizes that an individual's ability to adjust to their visual impairment is influenced by acceptance, recognition, and accommodation from parents, family, peers, and society. The active involvement of parents in daily activities, along with emotional intelligence and self-concept, can positively influence psychological adjustment.

Additionally, the study highlights that family life and peer influence independently and significantly predict academic adjustment in students with visual impairment. This supports the notion that the family's role is crucial in a visually impaired child's development, with parents exerting a major influence from birth to maturity. Consistency in parental attitude and ongoing support is essential during the early years of a visually impaired child's life.

In conclusion, the research establishes the effectiveness of family life and peer influence in positively influencing the academic adjustment of students with visual impairment. The correlation between family life, peer influence, and academic adjustment is significant both within and outside the school environment. Introducing intervention techniques related to family and peer support into the curriculum can benefit students, regardless of their visual impairment status.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

- School administrators should establish effective counseling services in all special schools. These would improve positive attitudinal change among students with visual impairment towards learning with the aim of fostering improved academic adjustment. Moreover, counseling psychologists and teachers in special schools should develop good management techniques in fostering positive peer influence among their students with or without impairment.

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- The concerned stakeholders in the education of the visually impaired should address positive peer influence among students with visual impairment through their efforts to build good academic adjustment and create environments in which students feel supported. The challenge is to reframe the understanding of self-concept that adolescent with visual impairment are focusing on the right strategies to foster their sense of competence and self-worth.
- It is also recommended that students with visual impairment be encouraged to join students' club and associations, this will promote healthy interaction and modelling or imitation of positive behaviours.

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